

A Review of the Effect of Pyrolysis Conditions of Biochar on Plant Growth

Aramide Adenike Adesina ✉, Moyosore Dorcas Abbey, Sarah Ibukunoluwa Shorinolu, Motunrayo Fatimah Yusuf, Oreoluwa Ruth Agbaje
Department of Chemical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Lagos State University, Nigeria

Abstract

The challenges of environmental pollution, and nutrient imbalances associated with the use of synthetic fertilizers to boost food production from increased plant growth have led to the paradigm shift to organic fertilization. In line with this is the production of biochar, an organic fertilizer from wastes and agricultural residues. However, the quality and effectiveness of biochar's agronomic application are a function of its properties directly linked to the process conditions used during production. This research work presents a review of the effect of pyrolysis conditions on the quality of biochar produced for plant growth. Specifically, the review discussed challenges of plant growth in agriculture, factors affecting plant growth, the use of biochar as an alternative organic fertilizer, the pyrolysis of biomass to biochar, factors affecting the properties of biochar and the effect of pyrolysis conditions as it affects the quality of biochar applied for plant growth and product. Another specific topic discussed is the future perspective towards biochar's wide application to different soil types. Biochar adoption in different types of soils will increase the versatility of its use in agriculture.

Keywords: *Pyrolysis, Biochar, Plant growth, Crop yield, Food security.*

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Introduction

Global food security faces mounting challenges as population growth intensifies pressure on agricultural production. Food shortages and reduced crop yields are increasingly common due to soil degradation, nutrient depletion, and the unsustainable practices associated with modern farming. Improving plant growth rates is central to enhancing food production, yet traditional methods such as synthetic fertilizer application present significant drawbacks, including environmental pollution, soil acidification, nutrient imbalances, and high economic costs (Kumar, Kumar, & Prakash, 2019; Qiao, et al., 2018).

Recent years have witnessed a paradigm shift in agricultural practices, with a growing emphasis on sustainable, eco-friendly approaches to boost crop productivity. Synthetic fertilizers, while effective in the short term, have contributed to long-term soil health deterioration, water pollution from nutrient runoff, and reduced soil microbial diversity (Rashmi, et al., 2020). These challenges underscore the urgent need for alternative fertilization strategies that can sustainably enhance plant growth without the negative side effects of conventional chemical inputs.

Biochar, a carbon-rich product generated by the pyrolysis of biomass, has emerged as a promising soil amendment and fertilizer alternative. Biochar can be produced from agricultural residues such as bean shafts (Adesina, et al., 2025) and offers multiple agronomic benefits, including improved soil structure, enhanced water retention, and increased nutrient availability (Diatta, et al., 2020; Li, et al., 2021). Importantly, the quality and efficacy of biochar are highly dependent on its production conditions. The parameters of the pyrolysis process, such as temperature, residence time, and heating rate, directly influence its physical and chemical properties (Amenaghawon, et al., 2021), which in turn determine its impact on plant growth.

Optimally produced biochar can serve a dual role in agriculture. As an inorganic fertilizer, it supplies essential nutrients and stabilizes soil pH, while its organic nature contributes to the enhancement of soil biological activity and overall fertility (Dangi, et al., 2020). This dual functionality helps to overcome the limitations of synthetic fertilizers by promoting sustainable nutrient cycling, reducing chemical dependency, and mitigating environmental risks.

Consequently, there is a need for research into optimizing biochar properties for plant growth. Although, research works have concentrated on the impact of pyrolysis conditions on biochar properties, others have been on studying the effect of biochar properties on soil conditions. An up-to-date state of the art in understanding the impact of pyrolysis conditions as it impacts the properties of biochar as required for plant growth is limited. Consequently, this study reviews the current state-of-the-art knowledge on how pyrolysis conditions impact the quality of biochar and its subsequent impact on plant growth. Ultimately, this research will add to the body of knowledge in providing sustainable pathways to improve plant growth rates, thereby addressing the challenges of food shortage. By recognizing the importance of these pyrolysis factors on biochar fertilizer quality, farmers, gardeners, and agricultural professionals can take steps to create an ideal environment for plant growth, leading to improved crop quality, increased productivity, and reduced environmental impact.

Plant Growth in Agriculture

Plant growth is a complex and dynamic process that is critical for crop yields and food production in agriculture. Understanding plant growth is essential for developing effective strategies to improve crop productivity, promote sustainable agriculture, and ensure global food security. Recent advances in plant genomics and biotechnology have provided new insights into the molecular mechanisms underlying plant growth and development (Sun, et al., 2024). These advances have also enabled the development of new crop varieties with improved growth characteristics and increased tolerance to environmental stresses. From the research of Fahad, et al. (2017), it was shown that plant growth is influenced by various physiological and biochemical processes, including photosynthesis, respiration, and nutrient uptake. These processes are regulated by a complex interplay of hormonal signals, genetic factors, and environmental stimuli. Photosynthesis is the primary process by which plants convert light energy into chemical energy, producing glucose and oxygen. Respiration is the process by which plants break down glucose to produce energy, releasing carbon dioxide and water as byproducts and nutrient uptake is the process by which plants absorb essential nutrients, such as nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium, from the soil (Marschner, & Rengel, 2023).

In agriculture, plant growth is often measured in terms of biomass production, leaf area index, and crop yield (Kamilaris, Kartakoullis, & Prenafeta-Boldú, 2017). These metrics provide valuable information on crop performance and can be used to evaluate the effectiveness of different management practices. Understanding plant growth is essential for developing effective strategies to improve crop productivity and promote sustainable agriculture. By optimizing plant growth

conditions, farmers can improve crop yields, reduce environmental impact, and promote sustainable agriculture.

Plant growth is crucial for food security, ecosystem services, and human well-being. Improved plant growth leads to increased crop yields, enhanced nutritional quality, and reduced poverty, ultimately contributing to food security (FAO, IFAD, UNICEF, WFP, & WHO, 2020). Additionally, plant growth supports ecosystem services, such as air and water filtration, soil erosion control, and climate regulation, which are essential for maintaining a healthy environment (Kumar, et al., 2024). Improved plant growth can improve physical health by enhancing air and water quality, and reducing pollution and toxins (Al-Kaisi, et al., 2017). Moreover, it supports mental health by providing a calming environment and reducing stress (Hassan, & Deshun, 2023). The growth also reduces poverty and improves livelihoods by providing food, fibre, and other essential products. The benefits of plant growth extend to the environment, where it plays a critical role in mitigating climate change by absorbing carbon dioxide and releasing oxygen. Plant growth also supports biodiversity, providing habitat and food for various species, and helps maintain ecosystem services, such as air and water filtration, soil erosion control, and climate regulation (Kamilaris, Kartakoullis, & Prenafeta-Boldú, 2017).

Plant growth rate is a critical factor in agriculture and achieving optimal plant growth rates is hindered by numerous challenges. Climate change, for instance, poses a significant threat to plant growth rates, as rising temperatures, changing precipitation patterns, and increased frequency of extreme weather events can all impact plant development (Lal, 2015). Soil degradation is another major challenge, as soil erosion, nutrient depletion, and salinization can reduce soil fertility and affect plant growth rates (Brisson, et al., 2010). Water scarcity, pests, and diseases also pose significant threats to plant growth rates, while nutrient deficiencies, weed competition, and temperature extremes can further limit plant development (Kumar, et al., 2024).

In addition, lack of pollinators, genetic limitations, fertilizer and pesticide overuse, inadequate farming practices, soil pH imbalance, microbial imbalance, and physical barriers can all impact plant growth rates (Lehmann, et al., 2015). These challenges can interact with each other and with other environmental factors, making it complex to manage plant growth rates in agriculture.

To overcome these challenges, farmers and agricultural experts must adopt integrated approaches that address the multiple factors affecting plant growth rates. This may involve implementing sustainable agricultural practices, developing climate-resilient crop varieties, and using precision agriculture techniques to optimize crop management. By understanding the complex interplay of factors affecting plant growth rates, effective strategies to promote optimal plant development and ensure global food security can be developed.

Factors Affecting Plant Growth

Plant growth is influenced by various factors, which can be broadly categorized into environmental, genetic, and agricultural factors (Fahad, et al., 2017).

Environmental Factors

Environmental factors play a crucial role in plant growth and development. Some of the key environmental factors affecting plant growth include: light intensity and quality, temperature, and soil composition.

- **Light intensity and quality**

Light intensity and quality both play significant roles in plant growth and development (Wu, et al., 2025). Increased light intensity can enhance photosynthesis, leading to increased plant growth and

productivity (Xu, Gao, & Ruan, 2015). Light intensity also influences plant morphology, including leaf orientation, stem elongation, and root growth. For example, plants grown in high-light conditions often have thicker stems and leaves, while those grown in low-light conditions may have longer stems and smaller leaves (Huché-Théliér, et al., 2016). Light intensity also affects flowering and fruiting in plants, with some plants requiring specific light intensities to initiate these processes (Luo, et al., 2023). For instance, some plants may require long days with high light intensity to produce flowers, while others may require shorter days with lower light intensity (Park, et al., 2016). In addition to light intensity, light quality also impacts plant growth and development. Different light spectra, such as blue, red, and far-red light, affect plant growth and development in distinct ways. Blue light promotes root growth, while red light enhances stem elongation (Li, et al., 2024). The duration of light exposure also affects plant growth and development. Plants have internal circadian clocks that respond to the duration and intensity of light exposure (Wei, Wang, & Yu, 2023) and this response affects various physiological processes, including photosynthesis, growth, and flowering. This shows that light intensity and quality are critical factors that regulate plant growth and development.

- **Temperature**

Temperature is a critical factor affecting plant growth, with plants having optimal temperature ranges for growth. Temperatures outside these ranges can significantly impact plant development. Temperature fluctuations affect plant growth in various ways, primarily through enzyme activity and water relations (Baloch, 2025). Enzyme activity is influenced by temperature, which in turn affects various plant processes, including growth and development. Optimal temperatures for enzyme activity vary among plant species but generally fall within a narrow range. Temperatures above or below this range can lead to reduced enzyme activity, impacting plant growth and productivity (Sher, et al., 2024). Temperature also affects plant water relations, including transpiration and water uptake. High temperatures can increase transpiration rates, leading to water loss and potential drought stress (Ke, et al., 2025). Conversely, low temperatures can reduce transpiration rates, leading to waterlogged soils and potential root rot (Miraj, 2024).

- **Soil composition**

Soil plays a vital role in plant growth by providing essential nutrients, water, and support. The quality, structure, and composition of soil significantly impact plant growth and development. Soil composition influences nutrient availability, which is crucial for plant growth and development. Nutrient-rich soils support healthy plant growth, while nutrient-poor soils can lead to stunted growth and reduced yields (Ahmed, et al., 2024). Soil pH also impacts plant growth, with most plants thriving in slightly acidic to neutral soils (pH 6.0-7.0). Soils with extreme pH levels can limit nutrient availability and hinder plant growth (Xia, et al., 2024). Soil organic matter is another critical factor influencing soil fertility, structure, and overall plant growth. Organic matter helps retain nutrients, improves soil structure, and supports beneficial microbial activity (Bot, & Benites, 2005).

Genetic Factors

Genetic factors play a significant role in influencing plant growth and development. The genetic makeup of a plant, including its breed, variety, and hybrid, can determine its growth habits, yields, and environmental adaptations (Araus, et al., 2008). Different plant breeds have distinct characteristics that set them apart from one another. Some breeds may be bred for their high yields, while others may be bred for their disease resistance or drought tolerance. Plant varieties, on the other hand, can exhibit variations in growth rate, maturity, and resistance to diseases and pests. These variations can be attributed to the genetic differences between varieties, some varieties may mature faster than others, while others may be more resistant to certain diseases or pests (Tooker, & Grettenberger, 2023). In addition, genetic factors can also impact a plant's nutritional content,

flavour, and texture. Some plant varieties may have higher levels of certain nutrients, such as vitamins or minerals, while others may have a sweeter or more desirable flavour.

Agricultural Factors

Agricultural factors, such as farming practices, have a significant impact on plant growth and development. Farming practices, including irrigation, fertilization, pruning, and pest management, significantly influence plant growth and yields. These practices ensure that plants receive the necessary water, nutrients, and care to thrive. Crop rotation, a type of agricultural practice, promotes plant growth through soil fertility, reducing pests and diseases, and increasing crop yields (Shah, et al., 2021). Soil conservation practices, such as contour farming and terracing, are also vital for promoting plant growth. These practices help to reduce soil erosion, retain moisture, and prevent nutrient depletion. Farmers can create a favourable environment for plant growth through the conservation of the soil health, leading to improved crop yields and sustainable agriculture (Shah, & Wu, 2019).

Fertilizers are substances added to soil to promote plant growth and fertility by providing essential nutrients such as nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium. Nitrogen is crucial for leaf growth, green colour, and protein synthesis while phosphorus is essential for root development, flower and fruit formation, and overall plant maturation. Potassium is important for overall plant health, resistance to disease, and water balance (Bumguardner, 2022). Fertilizers help plants grow stronger, healthier, and more productive, leading to improved crop yields and better food security.

The method of fertilizer application is a crucial step in promoting healthy plant growth and maximizing crop yields and has its advantages and disadvantages. The four common methods of fertilizer application are broadcasting, foliar application, drip irrigation, and injection. Broadcasting involves applying fertilizers uniformly over the soil surface, while foliar application involves spraying fertilizers directly onto the leaves of plants. Drip irrigation involves applying fertilizers through a network of tubes and drippers that deliver water and nutrients directly to the roots of plants, and injection involves injecting fertilizers into the soil or directly into the plant.

Fertilizer application timing also plays a crucial role in optimizing plant growth. The timing of fertilizer application can significantly impact the availability of essential nutrients for plants. The four critical stages for fertilizer application are pre-planting, planting, side-dressing, and foliar spray. At pre-planting, fertilizers are applied before planting to prepare the soil for seed germination. This stage is critical for creating a fertile soil environment that supports healthy seedling growth. At planting, fertilizers are applied to provide essential nutrients for seedling growth. This stage ensures that seedlings receive the necessary nutrients for establishment and early growth. For side-dressing, fertilizers are applied as a side-dressing to provide additional nutrients during plant growth. This stage helps to supplement the soil's nutrient supply, promoting healthy plant growth and development. For foliar spray, fertilizers are applied as a foliar spray to provide essential nutrients during plant growth. This stage allows for direct absorption of nutrients through the leaves, supporting plant growth and addressing nutrient deficiencies. Proper timing of fertilizer application ensures that plants receive the necessary nutrients at the right stage of growth.

There are two main types of fertilizers: synthetic fertilizers and organic fertilizers. Synthetic fertilizers, also known as inorganic fertilizers, are manufactured using chemical processes and provide quick nutrient release, promoting rapid plant growth (Sabry, 2015). Organic fertilizers, on the other hand, are derived from natural sources, such as animal waste, compost, and animal manure, and release nutrients slowly, promoting healthy plant growth.

Inorganic fertilizers provide excellent nutrients required for plant growth but environmental pollution resulting from its use is a major setback. The use of organic fertilizers from agricultural waste has been used to overcome the challenges of sustainability associated with the use of

inorganic fertilizers. One of such fertilizers is biochar. It is produced by combusting agricultural residues. It can increase soil carbon content, improve nutrient retention, and support beneficial microbial activity (Steinbeiss, Gleixner, & Antonietti, 2009).

Biochar as an Organic Fertilizer

Biochar is a carbon-rich material with a sponge-like texture that enables it to retain water as well as provide a habitat for some microbes when exposed to the atmosphere or applied to the soil. It usually looks like charcoal but it is produced specifically for environmental and agricultural use. Biochar is produced through the pyrolysis of biomass and provides several benefits for soil and plant growth, by providing essential nutrients, enhanced soil structure, aeration, and water-holding capacity, supporting robust root growth (Sossa, et al., 2024; Xue, et al., 2022). Additionally, biochar can store carbon in the soil for centuries, helping mitigate climate change by reducing soil erosion and increasing soil organic matter (Xue, et al., 2022). There are several types of biochar, including woody biochar and grassy biochar. Woody biochar is derived from wood biomass, while grassy biochar is produced from grassy biomass and has a faster nutrient release rate and higher nutrient content (Abhijeet, et al., 2020). By understanding the benefits and types of biochar, farmers and gardeners can harness its potential to create fertile soils, promote healthy plant growth, and contribute to a more sustainable environment.

Biochar Production from Pyrolysis

Pyrolysis is the process of using heat to break down the chemical bond in organic materials (biomass) at high temperatures in the absence of oxygen to give an irreversible product called biochar after cooling. Aside from biochar, pyrolysis also produces other valuable products such as bio-oil and syngas (Akhtar, Krepl, & Ivanova, 2018). Over time, pyrolysis has been known to be an effective process of obtaining energy in the form of char from biomass and is efficient as it produces little pollution when compared with combustion. The temperature range for the pyrolysis process occurs between 300-800 °C and the yield depends on the operating parameters such as temperature and residence time.

- **Principle of pyrolysis**

In most cases, the biomass to be used is first air-dried or sun-dried to reduce the moisture content until a constant weight is achieved. The biomass is then decomposed thermally in an oxygen-free medium resulting in the breakdown of the primary components of plant materials. The decomposition starts with the hemicellulose (200-300 °C) as it is the least thermally stable of the plant polymer. It is a branched, amorphous polysaccharide made of various sugar units, such as xylose, mannose, and arabinose. As heat increases, the weak bonds within hemicellulose start to break then the complex sugar chains decompose into volatile compounds (such as acetic acid, furfural, and carbon dioxide). As the temperature exceeds 300 °C, the cellulose (crystalline polymer of glucose) decomposes thereby breaking the glycosidic bonds linking glucose units. These glucose units undergo dehydration and fragmentation, forming anhydro sugars, levoglucosan, and other volatile compounds. Lastly, the lignin (the most thermally resistant of the plant components) decomposes over a temperature range of 400-600 °C. It is the complex aromatic polymer responsible for plant rigidity (El-Sayed, Khass, & Mostafa, 2024). Lignin's phenolic structures break apart thereby forming aromatic compounds, phenols, and tars. This process releases char and volatile gases more slowly than cellulose and hemicellulose and it contributes significantly to biochar formation. As the temperature rises beyond 600-800 °C, the remaining solid material (char) undergoes carbonization such that the volatile compounds continue to escape, leaving behind a stable, carbon-rich biochar.

- **Pyrolysis types**

Pyrolysis can be divided into seven subdivisions based on their operating conditions. Each subdivision has its advantages and disadvantages. This section discusses the types of pyrolysis main features and their operating conditions.

Slow pyrolysis

It is the gradual heating of organic materials which allows for a complete breakdown of the biomass promoting the formation of a stable carbon structure in the char. This process has been used for centuries in the production of charcoal but is now relevant in biochar production as well as carbon sequestration and energy recovery. It operates at relatively low temperatures (300-500 °C) with a slow heating rate (0.1- 1 °C/s), a long residence time greater than 1 h, and an atmospheric pressure of 1 atm (Waheed, Nahil, & Williams, 2013). The lower temperature (300 °C) favours char production, the higher temperature (500 °C) helps to produce more gas and liquid but still prioritises the char formation. The slow heating rate ensures thorough thermal degradation of biomass and high carbon retention in the char. The prolonged residence time allows for more complete decomposition which improves char quality. Slow pyrolysis produces char (30- 50%), bio-oil (15-30%) and syngas of about (20-40%) yield. This process is used when the objective is to obtain a high yield of char.

Fast pyrolysis

This type of pyrolysis requires the feedstock to be dried into finely ground biomass (particle size: 1–3 mm, moisture content: <10%) and then pyrolyzed in the absence of oxygen to produce bio-oil as the primary product, along with smaller amounts of gas and char. The high heating rate and short residence time in the reactor prevent the complete breakdown of organic compounds, favouring the formation of liquid intermediates. It operates between the temperature range of (400-600 °C) with a very high heating rate (10- 200 °C/s), a very short residence time (0.5 – 2 s) and an atmospheric pressure of 1 atm (Pahnila, et al., 2023). The optimal bio-oil was obtained at 500 °C, the rapid heating prevents extensive cracking of hydrocarbons thereby maximizing liquid production. The quick vapour removal prevents secondary reactions and char formation. Fast pyrolysis produces bio-oil (60- 75% by weight), char (10- 20% by weight) and syngas (10-20% by weight). This process is used when the objective is to maximize liquid yield, making it suitable for biofuel production and renewable energy generation.

Flash pyrolysis

This type of pyrolysis also requires the feedstock to be dried into finely ground biomass (particle size: <1 mm, moisture content: <10%). It is designed to maximize the production of bio-oil while minimizing char and gas formation. This process is commonly used for advanced biofuel production and chemical feedstock generation due to its high efficiency and product quality. It operates between the temperature range of 800-1000 °C with an extremely high heating rate (usually >1,000 °C/s), a very short residence time (typically <0.5 seconds) and at atmospheric pressure (Pahnila, et al., 2023). The higher temperatures favour bio-oil and gas production, with minimal char formation, the rapid heating prevents excessive degradation of the intermediate products, and vapours are immediately quenched to prevent secondary reactions as rapid cooling of pyrolysis vapours is crucial to condense them into bio-oil before they further decompose. Elevated pressures can increase gas yield but are less commonly used. Flash pyrolysis produces bio-oil (70–80% by weight), syngas (10–15% by weight) and char (5–10% by weight).

Hydropyrolysis

It requires the feedstock to be dried and finely ground for efficient heat transfer and reaction. It is an advanced form of pyrolysis that involves the thermal decomposition of biomass or organic

materials in the presence of high-pressure hydrogen gas. Hydropyrolysis facilitates the hydrogenation of pyrolysis products, reducing their oxygen content and improving the quality of bio-oil. It is useful for the production of high-quality biofuels, as the hydrogen prevents excessive cracking of hydrocarbons and stabilizes the liquid products (Marker, Felix, & Linck, 2013). It operates between the temperature range of 400 °C and 800 °C with high-pressure hydrogen ranging from 50 to 200 bar, moderate to high heating rate (10 to 200 °C/s), short to moderate residence time (typically a few seconds to minutes) and involves the use of catalysts such as nickel, molybdenum, or zeolites to enhance hydrocarbon formation and selectivity. The optimal bio-oil yield occurs around 500 °C to 600 °C. High pressure facilitates hydrogenation reactions thereby improving product quality while longer residence times increase gas yield but reduce liquid yield. Hydropyrolysis produces upgraded bio-oil (50–70% by weight), syngas (20–30% by weight) and char (10–20% by weight).

Catalytic pyrolysis

It requires dried, finely ground biomass (moisture content: <10%, particle size: 1–3 mm). Catalytic pyrolysis is an advanced form of pyrolysis where catalysts are introduced to enhance the thermal decomposition of biomass or organic materials. The presence of a catalyst alters the reaction pathways, promoting the formation of high-quality bio-oil, syngas and char while reducing undesirable byproducts such as oxygenated compounds (Sankaranarayanan, & Won, 2024; Zhang, et al., 2018). It operates between the temperature range (400- 700 °C), moderate to high heating rate (around 10 to 100 °C/s), and short to moderate residence time (2 to 10 s), and operates at atmospheric pressure although slightly elevated pressures can improve hydrocarbon yields. Catalysts such as zeolites (e.g. ZSM-5), metal oxides (e.g. TiO₂, Al₂O₃), alkaline catalysts (e.g. CaO, MgO) are used with a catalyst-to-biomass ratio of 0.1:1.0 by weight (Iminabo, 2023; Chireshe, 2019). The optimal bio-oil yield occurs around 450 °C to 550 °C. Higher temperatures favour gas production while rapid heating prevents excessive degradation of intermediates, and shorter residence times favour liquid yield while longer times increase gas and char production. Catalysts can be in situ (mixed with biomass) or ex-situ (placed in a separate catalytic reactor). Higher catalyst loading enhances cracking but increases costs and catalyst deactivation.

Catalytic Pyrolysis produces upgraded bio-oil (50–70% by weight), syngas (20–30% by weight) and char (10–20% by weight). This process is particularly beneficial for improving the bio-oil quality, reducing the oxygen content, and increasing the yield of valuable hydrocarbons, making it suitable for biofuel production and chemical synthesis.

Microwave pyrolysis

Microwave pyrolysis is an advanced thermal decomposition process where electromagnetic wave is used to heat biomass or organic materials, instead of conventional conductive or convective heating methods. The microwave radiation (915 MHz or 2.45 GHz) penetrates the material, causing polar molecules (like water and biomass components) to oscillate and generate internal heat. This results in uniform heating, faster reaction times, and efficient energy transfer. It operates between the temperature range of 300 – 800 °C, microwave frequency of 2.45 Hz, power of 300- 3000 W, uniform heating rate of 10 to 200 °C/min, residence time of 5 - 30 min, and atmospheric pressure. The use of a catalyst is optional (Allende, Brodie, & Jacob, 2023). Lower temperatures favour char formation, while higher temperatures increase bio-oil and gas yield. Shorter residence times increase liquid yield, while longer times favour char and gas formation.

Microwave pyrolysis produces bio-oil (40–60% by weight), Syngas (20–40% by weight) and biochar (10–30% by weight). Microwave pyrolysis is particularly advantageous for producing bio-oil, syngas, and biochar with enhanced energy efficiency and process control.

Plasma pyrolysis

It involves the use of plasma, an ionized gas composed of electrons, ions, and neutral particles that can reach extremely high temperatures (up to 10,000 °C) to break down biomass, organic waste, or other materials into syngas, bio-oil, and char. It operates at an extremely high heating rate due to the intense plasma energy, resulting in almost instantaneous pyrolysis, a very short residence time typically milliseconds to a few seconds, depending on the material and plasma intensity. Core plasma temperatures range from 3,000 °C to 10,000 °C and reaction zone temperatures range from 800 °C to 2,000 °C for pyrolysis at atmospheric pressure. The energy source is generated from plasma torches, powered by direct current (DC) arcs, radio frequency (RF) waves, or microwaves (Gabbar, et al., 2021). Plasma pyrolysis produces syngas (60–80% by weight), and bio-oil (10–20% by weight). This process not only converts biomass and waste into valuable products but also destroys hazardous compounds, making it useful for waste treatment and energy recovery.

Pyrolysis Conditions, Feedstock and Biochar Properties

The physicochemical properties of biochar, including its porosity, surface area, elemental composition, and stability, are largely influenced by the pyrolysis conditions under which it is produced (Li, et al., 2023; Muzyka, et al., 2023). Understanding these parameters is crucial for optimizing biochar characteristics for specific applications. It is essential to comprehend the pyrolysis conditions that govern biochar's final properties. The influence of temperature, heating rate, residence time, feedstock type, particle size, atmospheric conditions, and pressure all play crucial roles in determining biochar's physical and chemical attributes. Each of these factors must be carefully controlled to achieve the desired biochar characteristics, whether for agricultural, industrial, or environmental applications.

- **Pyrolysis temperature**

Pyrolysis temperature significantly influences the physicochemical properties of biochar, affecting its yield, carbon and ash content, surface area, and functional groups. For a particular feedstock, increasing the pyrolysis temperature from 500 to 700 °C resulted in increases in surface area, ash content, pH, phosphorus and calcium content while the yield and cation exchange capacity (CEC) decreased (Wang, et al., 2013). The effect of pyrolysis temperature on other biochar properties such as thermal stability and volatile compounds has also been assessed.

Conz, et al. (2017) examined the effect of biochar feedstock from different sources: rice hull, poultry litter, sawdust, and sugarcane straw, and pyrolysis temperature on the physicochemical properties of biochar. Findings show that increasing pyrolysis temperature supported biochar stability irrespective of the feedstock type. However, the agricultural properties of the char varied with feedstock type and pyrolysis temperature.

Rodriguez, et al. (2020) studied the effect of agricultural and industrial waste-generated biochars and temperature on the properties of the produced biochars. The findings reveal that increased temperature reduced pH in water, solids yield, volatile compounds and soluble potassium in all produced biochars. However, an increase in temperature did not affect the chemical properties such as electrical conductivity, cation exchange capacity (CEC), and water-soluble nutrients in biochars from industrial wastes.

- **Heating rate**

The heating rate during pyrolysis significantly influences the properties of biochar, affecting its yield, porosity, surface area, and carbon content. Biochars produced at different heating rates show different distributions across their physical and chemical properties which is vital for their effectiveness in their application.

Recent studies have demonstrated the effect of different factors and pyrolysis heating rate on the properties of the produced biochar. Accordingly, Zhao, et al. (2018) studied the combined effect of pyrolysis temperature (200-700 °C), heating rates (1-20 °C/min) and residence times (10-100 min) on the properties of rapeseed biochar. Although temperature had the most influence on the properties of biochar such as pH, fixed ash content, carbon content, and microporous structure, the surface area and morphology were greatly influenced by the heating rate. The heating rate however does not have a significant on the yield and pH of the biochar.

Bartoli, et al. (2022) also studied the combined influence of temperature (500-700 °C), and slow and fast heating rates on the electrical conductivity of biochar from sewage sludge, walnut shells and lignin-rich residue. Results of the study show that the heating rate and temperature at 500 and 600 °C had a marginal effect on the electrical conductivity of biochar. However, the lowest electrical conductivity of biochar from walnut shells was irrespective of the temperature and heating rate.

Heating rates also affect the carbonization and energy value of biochar. High heating rates enhance carbonization and the stability of biochar under high temperatures while low heating rates enhance high heating value of biochar. Li, et al. (2021) studied the effect of heating rate on the functionalities of biochar. A high heating rate with a short reaction time resulted in biochar with a low energy yield and heating value and facilitated the cracking of more organic and volatile components of the biochar. This led to the formation of more gases. Consequently, biochars produced at a high heating rate and high temperatures are more suited for fuel application due to the high heating value and less volatile matter content. However, temperature has a more pronounced effect on the biochar properties than other conditions (Angin, 2013).

- **Residence time**

Residence time, the duration for which biomass is subjected to pyrolysis conditions, significantly influences the properties of the resulting biochar. The residence time and temperature have a combined effect on the properties of biochar. At a low pyrolysis temperature of 300 °C and increasing the residence time, the yield of biochar reduced while the pH and iodine adsorption number increased. However, increasing the residence time at an increased temperature of 600 °C had little effect on the yield and pH while the iodine adsorption number was reduced (Sun, et al., 2017).

Recent studies have demonstrated these effects under various conditions: Wang, et al. (2013) studied the effect of temperature and residence time on biochar properties from different feedstocks. The findings of the study reveal that increasing the residence time from 4-16 h increased the BET surface area and ash content. However, the yield decreases with an increase in residence time.

Findings from the work of Wang, et al. (2020) showed that the residence time and temperature had a direct relationship with biochar properties. Nutrient retaining ability, ash content, electrical conductivity, pH, and oxidation stability increased with increasing temperature and residence time while the available nutrients were reduced. Consequently, a higher residence time is not well suited for biochars applied for agricultural purposes.

- **Feedstock type**

The type of biomass feedstock used in biochar production significantly influences its physicochemical properties, including stability, carbon content, and functional groups. The intrinsic nature of the biomass used for producing the biochar is one of the factors affecting the derived char (Sun, et al., 2017). Recent studies have demonstrated these effects using various feedstocks:

Biochar produced from different woody biomass does not show an effect on the properties of the biochar because the feedstock was both woody legumes (Cárdenas-Aguilar, et al., 2024). However, studies using different types of biomass feed showed a profound effect on the properties of biochar.

Sun, et al. (2017) studied the effect of pyrolysis temperature and residence time on biochar obtained from eight different feedstocks. Results of the findings reveal that low agricultural waste such as wheat straw can be pyrolysed at low temperatures of 300 °C and a time of 2 h while high ash agricultural waste such as sweet potato vine can be pyrolysed at the same temperature but a longer reaction time of 4 h.

- **Particle size**

Biomass particle size significantly influences heat transfer and pyrolysis efficiency, thereby affecting the characteristics of the resulting biochar. The stability of biochar is a function of the particle size of the biomass used for pyrolysis. At high temperatures and with fine particle size, the biochar produced had a higher stability compared to that produced with larger particle size (Abbas, et al., 2018). From the work of Manyà, et al. (2014), the particle size of the biomass is the most significant factor used to determine the stability of biochar amongst other factors such as pressure and peak temperatures. The classification of the produced biochar into nanopores, mesopores and micropores is a function of the biomass particle size.

Muzyka, et al. (2023) demonstrated the impact of the following grain sizes: below 0.2 mm, 0.5–1 mm, 1–2 mm, and 2–3.15 mm and their relationship with other different parameters on the pore size distribution sorption, and porosity of biochars prepared at different pyrolytic temperatures. At a heating rate of 20 °C/min, grain size of 0.5–1.0 mm, and a residence time of 5 min, a pore size of 2.34 nm, and a high surface area of 400 m²/g were obtained at 700 °C.

Abbas, et al. (2018) studied the impact of the following different particle sizes: less than 200, 100–200, 50–100 and 10–50 mesh sizes on the bulk characteristics and surface chemistry of rice-husk-derived biochar. Results reveal that the carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen content reduced with reduced biomass particle size while the other elements such as oxygen and sulphur increased with reduced particle size. The volatile and ash content increases with decreasing particle size while the fixed carbon content reduces with reducing particle size. The micropore surface area, pH, pore volume and particle surface area were reduced by reducing particle size up to 10–50 mesh size.

- **Atmosphere and gas flow rate**

The pyrolysis environment, including the type of atmosphere and gas flow rate, significantly influences biochar properties. Conducting pyrolysis in an inert atmosphere (e.g. nitrogen or argon) promotes fixed carbon retention, while limited oxygen exposure can enhance the formation of functional groups beneficial for applications like pollutant adsorption. The presence of steam or carbon dioxide during pyrolysis can lead to activation effects, increasing biochar's surface area and reactivity. Manipulating gas flow rates further affects the interaction between volatile compounds and biochar, influencing pore development and elemental composition. Recent studies have demonstrated these effects:

Abbas, et al. (2018) studied the combined influence of gas flow rate (20–200 standard cm³ min⁻¹) and other pyrolysis conditions on the surface chemistry and bulk characteristics of rice husk biochar. The carbon content reduced while the oxygen content increased with increasing gas flow rate. The ash content increased while the volatile content reduced with increasing gas flow rate. In terms of the surface area, pH and electrical conductivity, the pH reduced with increasing gas flow rate, while the surface area, micropore surface area and pore volume increased with increasing gas flow rate.

- **Pressure**

High-pressure pyrolysis significantly influences biochar properties by affecting volatile release dynamics, pore formation, and mechanical strength. The pressure is measured as a function of the gas residence time within the reactor. Manyà, et al. (2013) studied the effect of pressure (0.1-1.5 Mpa) and a peak temperature of 400-550 °C on the biochar and fixed carbon yield. Findings showed that the biochar yield decreased with increasing pressure and peak temperature while the fixed-carbon content increased with increasing pressure and temperature. The rate of devolatilization of biomass increased at intermediate pressures of 0.8 Mpa.

In terms of biochar stability, the most stable biochar produced from olive mill waste from the work of Manyà, et al. (2014) was observed at the highest pressure of 1.1 Mpa and 600 °C using slow pyrolysis. Manyà, et al. (2013) studied the effect of pyrolysis pressure of biochar obtained from vine shoots, a waste from the wine industry. Findings showed that the absolute pressure did not play a significant role in the stability of the biochars from vine shoots. However, the largest hydrogen content of the biochars was obtained at atmospheric pressure and the highest peak temperature of up to 800 °C. Consequently, the effect of pressure on the properties of biomass is a function of other operating parameters such as temperature. Also, high-pressure pyrolysis compromises biochar's surface area and porosity (Manyà, 2012). This trade-off is critical when designing biochar for specific applications, such as structural materials where stability is prioritized over adsorption capacity. Optimizing pyrolysis pressure conditions based on the intended use of biochar is essential for maximizing its functional properties.

Biochar Properties and Their Impact on Plants

The effects of biochar on plants are primarily determined by its physicochemical properties, which are influenced by factors such as feedstock type, pyrolysis temperature, and post-production treatments. Understanding these properties and their interactions with soil and plants is essential for optimizing biochar applications in agriculture and environmental management.

Physical Properties

The physical characteristics of biochar, such as porosity, surface area, and particle size, play a crucial role in its interaction with soil and plant roots. Biochar has a high surface area, which enables it to absorb and retain nutrients and water. Its low bulk density makes it easy to mix with soil and other amendments, allowing for seamless integration into existing soil ecosystems. When biochar is produced from smaller biomass particles and under moderate pyrolysis temperatures (400–500 °C), it tends to have a well-developed porous structure, which enhances soil aeration and water-holding capacity. Verheijen, et al. (2019) found that biochar derived from agricultural residues with a particle size of less than 1 mm significantly improved soil moisture retention, leading to enhanced root penetration and increased plant growth.

Additionally, biochar's bulk density influences soil structure and compaction. Light and low-density biochars, such as those produced from wood chips, can help loosen compacted soils, promoting root development. Conversely, heavier biochars may clog soil pores and contribute to soil compaction when applied in high quantities (Lin, et al., 2024).

Chemical Properties

The chemical composition of biochar, including pH, cation exchange capacity (CEC), and elemental content, significantly affects soil nutrient availability and plant health. Biochar pH varies depending on feedstock and pyrolysis conditions as discussed in section 4. Its pH-dependent surface charge enables it to adapt to changing soil conditions, hence, it can be used to balance soil

pH and ensure optimal performance across various soil types. In line with this Salem, et al. (2019) studied the effect of biochar having a pH of 7.6 on soil and plants. Results revealed that the yield of potatoes decreased by 6% due to the alkalinity of biochar which increased the alkalinity of soils which might precipitate the soil nutrients making it unavailable for plant growth. Also, biochar has been used to improve saline-alkaline soils due to the buffering capacity of soil and its alkaline properties (Chen, et al., 2024). Consequently, optimizing pyrolysis conditions which will produce biochar well suited for a specific application is necessary. Biochar produced at low temperatures (300 °C), a time of 2 h can be used to improve the alkalinity of soils while biochar produced at the same temperature but at a longer residence time of 4 h can be used to improve acidic soils (Wang, et al., 2013).

Arif, et al. (2017) studied the effect of biochar on a maize-wheat rotation experiment on alkaline soils for 2 years. Findings revealed that the application of biochar significantly increased grain yield, soil organic carbon (SOC), and available phosphorus and nitrogen contents without any adverse effects on electrical conductivity and soil pH.

Chemically, biochar boasts a CEC, which allows it to retain positively charged ions (cations) and exchange them with other cations. This property enhances soil fertility by providing a steady supply of essential nutrients. Biochar with a high CEC can adsorb and release essential nutrients, reducing leaching losses and improving plant nutrient uptake.

Domingues, et al. (2020) applied biochars from different feedstocks; chicken manure, eucalyptus saw dust, sugarcane bagasse and coffee husk, pyrolysed at different temperatures to enhance the CEC of soil. Results revealed that the feedstock, pyrolysis temperature and biochar addition rate were factors controlling the CEC of soils. Further results reveal that the CEC of soils increases with high ash CEC of biochar and the application rate.

In desert soils, biochar has been shown to improve plant growth by increasing the CEC of the soil. Laghari, et al. (2016) studied the effect of biochars in improving the quality of desert soils and plant growth. Results revealed that moisture depletion with depth was reduced with the addition of biochar to desert soils. The soil water holding capacity improved by 14 and 57% at pyrolysis temperatures of 400 and 700 °C respectively. Soil hydraulic conductivity was reduced by 15% and 42%, and moisture-retention capacity was improved by 16% and 59%. Consequently, there was an increase in the yield of sorghum planted on the soil by 19 and 32% at temperatures 400 and 700 °C. Biochar also improves other chemical properties such as the water retention capacity and soil organic carbon (Mohamed, et al., 2016).

Biological Properties

Biochar also influences soil microbial communities, which play a vital role in plant growth through nutrient cycling and organic matter decomposition. The surface chemistry and porosity of biochar create habitats for beneficial microorganisms, fostering symbiotic relationships that enhance plant nutrient uptake.

Tang, et al. (2020) studied the effect of pyrolysis temperature of biochar derived from *solidago canadensis* L on plant-soil microbes. Results showed that the main driving forces for the composition of the bacterial community were organic matter, carboxylic acids, soil bulk density, phenolic acids and amines present in biochar. Consequently, high-temperature biochar (above 550 °C) was more effective as a soil amendment in saline-alkaline soils due to less amount of toxic hydrocarbons such as phenols, amines and carboxylic acids, more beneficial soil bacteria and it supported the growth of *solidago canadensis* L unlike low-temperature biochar (below 550 °C) which contains these compounds.

Dangi, et al. (2020) studied the effect of biochar soil amendment on soil micro-organisms for 2 years. Results showed that the amounts of Gram-negative and positive bacteria, bacterial phospholipid fatty acid (PLFA) and *arbuscular mycorrhizal fungal* (AMF), increased significantly at increasing biochar rates compared to those unfertilized, non-amended soils and lower biochar rates.

Although biochar application to the soil favours soil microorganisms, certain soil microbial communities are not favoured. In line with this, Anderson, et al. (2011) studied the effect of biochar application on a wide range of soil micro-organisms in a pot experiment. Results revealed that there was a 14% increase in *Hyphomicrobiaceae*, a 6% increase in *Streptosporangineae*, an 8% increase in *Bradyrhizobiaceae* and an 8% increase in *Thermomonosporaceae*. However, for *Streptomyetaceae* and *Micromonosporaceae* there was an 11 and 7% decrease in their abundance respectively compared to the control.

Despite the selective impact of biochar on the microbial community, its addition to soils promotes nitrogen-fixing bacteria, nitrate reduction to ammonium bacteria, nitrification of ammonium to nitrite bacteria, and adsorbs ammonium in soils. Consequently, N₂O emissions from soils are reduced with the application of biochar (Anderson, et al., 2011). Hence, improving the overall health of the ecosystem.

Zhang, et al. (2018) also assessed the impact of biochar produced at specific pyrolysis conditions on the soil microbial community. Results reveal that low-temperature biochar significantly increased the fungi-to-bacteria ratio of soils with low pH and nutrients. The application of biochar improved the stability of the ecosystem.

Co-Interaction with Fertilizers and Soil Amendments

Biochar's ability to interact with fertilizers and soil amendments plays a critical role in determining its agricultural benefits. When applied alongside fertilizers, biochar can improve nutrient retention and reduce losses due to leaching. In the studies of Dangi, et al. (2020), the co-application of biochar and organic fertilizer increased the yield of pepper plants compared to unfertilized soils and organic nitrogen fertilizers.

The combined use of biochar with organic fertilizers can also improve the growth of soil microorganisms in the management of plant diseases. Yuan, et al. (2021) studied the combined effect of biochar, compost and plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria on tomato plants. Results showed that there was an 80% suppression in *B. subtilis* disease when biochar was used alone. Also, tomato plant growth and physiological parameters were significantly higher when biochar was used in combination with plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria. This suggests that biochar can serve as an effective tool for suppressing microorganism-causing diseases while supporting plant growth in polluted environments.

Optimizing Pyrolysis Conditions for Biochar Impact on Plant Growth and Productivity

The cumulative effect of biochar's physical, chemical, and biological properties directly influences plant growth and crop productivity. To harness the full potential of biochar for plant growth, pyrolysis conditions must be carefully optimized. Moderate temperatures (400–600 °C), slow heating rates, and appropriate feedstocks are key to producing biochar that balances nutrient retention, carbon stability, and soil health benefits. Proper ageing or composting of biochar can mitigate phytotoxicity, while soil testing can help tailor biochar application to specific soil conditions (Hameed, et al., 2024).

Multiple studies have reported significant improvements in biomass production, root development, and overall plant health when biochar is applied at optimal rates. However, excessive biochar application can lead to negative effects. Chandra and Bhattacharya (2019) optimized pyrolysis temperature and time for biochar homogeneity and its further application in soils and plant growth. Results reveal that the optimized temperature and pyrolysis time to achieve the maximum seedling growth with the following biochar properties pH (8-9), yield (35–40%), nitrogen (3–4%), carbon (35–40%) and ash (32–35%), CEC (40–45 cmol/kg), C: N (22–25:1), O: C (0.7–0.8), and low volatiles (44–48%), was 500 to 600 °C and 80 to 100 min.

Suthar, et al. (2018) studied the effect of pyrolysis conditions in producing biochar that will improve plant growth and fruit quality. Results showed that biochars produced at 300 °C and amended at 3% or pyrolyzed at 450 °C and amended at 1% increased plant growth index. Contents of glucose, fructose, soluble solids, ascorbic acid, and sugar-to-acid ratios of fruits produced from the two treatments were significantly higher than the other treatments.

Bian, et al. (2022) examined the case study of the co-pyrolysis of food waste and rice husk as a soil amendment in China. The compounded fertilizer significantly improved the yield and quality of Chinese cabbage. Therefore, site-specific assessments and tailored application rates are necessary to maximize biochar’s benefits while avoiding potential drawbacks. A summary of different works on the effect of pyrolysis conditions of biochar on plant growth is given in Table 1.

Table 1. Summary of Research Works on the Effect of Pyrolysis Conditions of Biochar on Plant Growth and Soils

Biochar feedstock	Pyrolysis conditions	Optimum conditions	Biochar properties	Plant type	Soil type	Findings	Reference
Rice straw	Temperature, time duration	80–100 min respectively.	C (35–40%), N (3–4%), ash (32–35%), yield (35–40%), CEC (40–45 cmol /kg), C: N (22–25:1), low O: C (0.7–0.8), pH (8–9), and low volatiles (44–48%).	Mung beans	-	There was a direct correlation between seed growth and nutrients increase in biochar samples at all pH values	Chandra, & Bhattacharya, (2019)
Bamboo	Temperature	300 °C, 3% soil amendment and 450 °C, 1% soil amendment	pH(6.7,5 .2), Ca (0.135, 0.146), Fe (0.033, 0.047),	Tomato	Sand	Increased plant growth index, sugars, sugar-to-acid ratio	Suthar, et al.. (2018)

			K(0.794, 1.067), Na (0.428, 0.48), Mg (0.131, 0.158)			and ascorbic acid in fruit increased.	
Food waste +rice husk	Temperature	-	20 % yield, C (433 g/kg)	Chinese Cabbage	-	Fruit yield and quality improved significantly, and plant uptake of heavy metals was reduced.	Bian, et al. (2022)
-	-	-	-	Lodgepole pine, sitka alder	Temperate and boreal soil	Pine, alder greater biomass, increased soil pH, exchangeable cations	Robertson, et al. (2012)
Sawdust	Temperature	700 °C	pH (6.36-9.31), electrical conductivity (0.57-2.44dsm ⁻¹) C (517-744), N (9.3-5.6gkg ⁻¹)	Sorghum	Desert soil	Increased yield of 32%, water retention capacity of 57%. Improved total carbon, CEC and plant nutrient	Laghari, et al. (2016)
Birch	Temperature	No optimum	pH (5.1-7.5), C (72-89%), H (4.9-3.1%), N(0.2-0.3%), O(23-7%), S (0.1% each)	Lettuce, radish, barley, ryegrass	Sandy-silt	The impact of temperature was plant-specific. Birch biochar (20g/L) increased radish root yield but there was no effect of biochar on barley biomass production.	Hagner, et al. (2016)
Eucalyptus wood, greenhouse waste	Temperature, feedstock, concentration	Feedstock type suppressed diseases more (1%	-	Cucumber	-	<i>Rhizoctonia solani</i> disease suppression	Jaiswal, et al. (2014)

		eucalyptus wood biochar and 5% greenhouse waste biochar)				in cucumber	
Switchgrass	Temperature, catalyst	Similar performance of biochar at 300 and 400 °C	C (28-35%), H (1.7-1.1%), N (0.5-0.44%), O (11.4-16.6%), K (304.3-216.2%), P (168.3-69.2%), Mg (4.5-12.9%), Ca (14.2-19.0%)	Wheat	Heavy metal contaminated sandy soil	Increased pH, CEC, and soil nutrients. Decreased phytotoxicity and uptake of Co, Pb and Ni. Improved plant growth	Mohamed, et al. (2021)
Agricultural waste	Temperature	Biochar at 350 °C was the earliest to grow and at 600 °C, it supported the best growth.	-	Strawberry	-	Biochar pyrolysed at different temperatures grew better growth and flowered earlier.	Yuan, Liang, & Yang, (2025)

Conclusion and Future Perspective

A study on the assessment of the current state-of-the-art knowledge on how pyrolysis conditions impact the quality of biochar and its subsequent impact on plant growth has been carried out. The cumulative effect of biochar's physical, chemical, and biological properties directly influences its subsequent application. In agriculture, the effectiveness of the use of biochar to improve plant growth and crop productivity is a direct effect of its properties which is linked to the conditions used during pyrolysis. To harness the full potential of biochar for plant growth, pyrolysis conditions must be carefully optimized. Moderate temperatures (400–600°C), slow heating rates, and appropriate feedstocks are key to producing biochar that balances nutrient retention, carbon stability, and soil health benefits. Recognizing the importance of these pyrolysis factors on biochar fertilizer quality will help farmers take steps to create an ideal environment for plant growth.

However, studies focusing on the optimization of pyrolysis conditions to produce low pH biochars that will be suited specifically for alkaline soils are very limited. Consequently, further optimization studies on assessing pyrolysis conditions for producing biochars specifically suited for alkaline soils and plants grown on them are needed. Although, optimization studies have been centred on saline-alkaline soils and acidic soils, optimizing biochars specifically for alkaline soils to enhance plant growth on alkaline soils are recent areas that need further studies. Biochar adoption in different types of soils will increase the versatility of its use in agriculture.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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